
Editorial: The inaugural issue

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Background

“What were we thinking?”, we asked one another quite regularly during the last year. Starting a new journal in the middle of a pandemic, in the middle of a reviewing crises with well-established journals struggling to find reviewers, in the middle of the daily mess that all of us had to deal with in one shape or form (Nathalie: all I am saying is ironing board standing desk). So, before we introduce the journal, we want to say thank you! Thank you to our authors for their patience and understanding as we tried to learn new software, stalked reviewers, and fished emails from spam folders. Thank you so much to all our reviewers for last minute rescue missions, patience, and enormous amounts of good will to meet with authors, provide personal feedback and just being all around amazing.

Now to the official part...

We are delighted to announce and share with you the inaugural issue of the *Open Scholarship of Teaching and Learning journal*. Its inception was born of rejection, after a paper Vicki and I wrote with our students repeatedly could not find a home, because it just did not fit into the strict rules of existing journals. So, after experiencing power brokering in gate keeping and hitting walls when trying to challenge the notions of power in knowledge creation, here we are with a journal that is not only open access but also open peer review. There is no hiding behind anonymity when providing feedback. We believe the peer feedback process should be part of an open and transparent discourse, it should be a debate the authors, reviewers, and sometimes editors enter jointly. In situations where the authors are in their early career stages or new to writing in the field of Scholarship of Learning and Teaching (SoTL), we encourage the peer reviewers to take on a mentoring role, meet together, provide guidance and feedback. We also encourage submissions that are imperfect, thinking out loud, things that didn't work, things that are not just written words. And we are delighted that our inaugural issue reflects all of this from traditional papers to spoken word art. We share knowledge creation that empowers the authors and validates different forms of knowing and learning.

Without further ado we now hand over to the authors and wish you enjoyment, learning, and a bit of fun reading this first issue.

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